

INCREASING SOCIAL AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN.

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Abstract: Studying the importance of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan today to increase the socio-political activity of women and the measures taken to support women, taking into account our history and our current situation in the implementation of tasks, analysis and development of necessary proposals and recommendations is of urgent importance. One of the common features of political processes is that the main source of the political process in any country is the conscious activity of the public. If people take an active part in the political life of the society, the political processes will accelerate, and in such conditions, the active action of any political institutions will give its effective result. As political activity marks the conscious political activity of people and the progress of political processes, it requires the active participation of every member of the society in the political work carried out in the state.

Key words: women, politics, political activism, "women's wing", social activism, *social and political activity*.

The family is one of the ancient institutions of civil society, which has followed a complex path of development. Man alone would not have been able to survive in primitive times. In primitive times, man lived as a —Big family, people in it had close relationships and were separated only into the category of parents and children. The emergence of interest in the family problem is not accidental, because for several thousand years the family has been the basis of society and they have been directly influencing each other. Not much attention was paid to the legal aspect, stressing that the family, marriage is divinely established by the priests and the church. A family should be understood as a small society of one person, the union of a man and a woman is the basis of this society. This family may consist of children born from the union of one woman and a man or several women and men, and there may be mutual rights and obligations between them, and these rights and obligations may be regulated by customs and laws. These families live under one household or can live in several houses as family groups. The dictionary defines a family as a group of close relatives who live together. In the philosophical dictionary, it is explained that the family is a form of creating personal living conditions as a form of social society, and it is a common economy based on relationships between men and women, parents and children, siblings and other relatives based on kinship and conjugal relations.

Currently, women make up 45 percent of the workers and employees working in various fields and industries in our country. In particular, about 1400 women are working in leadership positions in the system of state and public organizations. 17 of them are senators, 16 are deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, and 1075 are members of local councils of people's deputies. Dozens of our sisters are "Hero of Uzbekistan", "Scientist of Uzbekistan", "People's Teacher of Uzbekistan", "People's Poet of Uzbekistan", "People's Artist of Uzbekistan", etc. received titles, orders and medals. Among them, more than 500 doctors of science and academicians, thousands of candidates of science are diligently serving the development of our country with their knowledge and talent. The medal "Reputable Woman" was established for

women who have shown activity and initiative in the life of society and the state, who have made a worthy contribution to the formation and well-being of the family, the protection of motherhood and childhood through their effective work.

Protecting the reproductive health of women and girls, making them healthy, and developing special health programs for women of different genders is one of the issues of high social necessity and meeting the requirements of the current state policy, in particular, the Decree on the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Reproductive health of girls is inextricably linked with preservation of the nation's gene pool, protection of public health, introduction of preventive medicine practice, promotion of healthy lifestyle and implementation. Despite the measures taken, there are also specific problems related to strengthening the health of mothers and children and women. Among them, conducting targeted research on socio-economic factors affecting the level of maternal mortality, measures to prevent anemia, changing the local mindset on pregnancy care, forming a loving attitude towards pregnant women, involving men in these issues, increasing their thinking and knowledge on the basics of reproductive health, anemia, tuberculosis, as well as the wide distribution of medical information about the consequences of iodine deficiency and iron deficiency, and taking measures to prevent reproductive diseases.

Institutions of civil society have a great role in ensuring the rights and freedoms of women and increasing their social and political activity. Because public organizations of a non-state nature, representing the interests of various groups and strata, are today recognized as an important institution of modern civil society. By widely involving women in such organizations, it is possible to ensure their rights and freedoms, and at the same time, their direct and indirect participation in state and community management is ensured. Today, the work carried out with women working in the fields of science and education in our country can be divided into two directions. After all, 72% of the employees working in this field are women. The first direction is to further increase the socio-political activity of women working in educational institutions, to further improve the work of ensuring their active participation in the reforms implemented in our country, and this direction is the development of our country. is one of the important factors. This task can be implemented by further strengthening the activities of primary organizations in educational institutions. In particular, paying attention to increasing the economic and legal knowledge of women in educational institutions, strengthening prevention of delinquency and crime, and ensuring that teachers observe the dress code and etiquette are also an important component of the reforms carried out in our country today.

In conclusion, it should be noted that women in Uzbekistan actively participate in the political life of the state and society, the reforms implemented have created the necessary opportunities for ensuring the rights and freedoms of our women, intellectual and spiritual growth. Based on the above, we believe that it is important to carry out the following activities in order to increase the socio-political activity of women in the society: First, it is appropriate to conduct scientific and practical research on the increase of political and social activity of women. Also, in determining the research topics, it is appropriate to proceed from the tasks defined in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan to increase the socio-political activity of women; Secondly, conducting scientific-practical conferences and sociological surveys aimed at increasing the political and social activity of women became important; Third, take advantage of various interactive services to increase women's chances of becoming members of a political party. It is

appropriate for each political party to review the activities of "women's wings" and expand the scope of projects and activities aimed at increasing the political activity of women.

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